

CATTLE PASTORALISTS' STRATEGIES TO COPE WITH WATER SCARCITY IN CLIMATE CHANGE CONTEXT IN NORTHERN BENIN, WEST AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the strategies cattle pastoralists use to cope with the shortage of water resources along their grazing routes. A computational approach is combined with socio-anthropological methods. This enables us to learn more from the local actors' thinking and acting process in the context of vulnerability. During three months, 30 cattle herds were partially followed along an international animal route in the north of Benin, in order to understand the mechanisms through which they accessed water during the inimical season. Individual interviews and focus group discussions were utilised to elicit information on pastoral activities. Our results reveal a pastoral dynamics based on the programmed distance to the best resources, the duration of resource-gathering stays, the livestock market position along the route and the possibility of overdigging wells. These are the strategies pastoralists use to adapt to climate change. The findings suggest that an actor-oriented policy and local resource use planning could be useful in managing the movement of herbivorous livestock in open range. This could also enhance adaptation to climate change within the context of the West African indigenous livestock system.

Keywords: Climate Change, Water resources, Pastoralist, Animal route, Adaptation Strategy, Benin

BACKGROUND

Human sustenance depends essentially on water, extracted directly from rivers or from reservoirs (Barnett *et al.* 2005). Global warming will increase evaporation and severely reduce rainfalls in certain regions. We cannot deny the fact that water resources are changing around the world due to climate change. The potential impacts are particularly severe in semi-arid and arid regions because of the sensitivity of such hydrological cycles to small change in climate variables (Arora *et al.* 2008; Zhang *et al.* 2009; Lioubimtseva and Henebry, 2009). By 2100, about one billion to three billion people worldwide are projected to suffer from water scarcity (Gorbatchev and Severino, 2007). The scarcity of this symbolic, spiritual and human life based element is predicted to exert considerable stress and exacerbate conflicts worldwide. Africa is one of the first regions adversely affected, because of its predominant location in the tropics, its dependence on natural resources and various socioeconomic, demographic and policy trends that limit the adaptive capacity of African countries and enhance their vulnerability (Morton, 2007; Madzwamuse, 2010; Olorunfemi, 2011). Avoiding emerging conflicts or "water wars" will depend on the collective capacity to anticipate tensions and to find the technical and institutional solutions to

manage them (Gorbatchev and Severino, 2007; Hendrix and Salehyan, 2012).

The Republic of Benin is located between the Gulf of Benin and the valley of Niger (6°17 to 12°04 North latitude) and integrates the Dahomey gap, a rain forest fragmentation characterized by a decline in annual rainfall, a fluctuation of temperatures causing a climate anomaly (Bokonon-Ganta, 1987; Hayward and Oguntoyinbo, 1987; Salzmann and Hoelzmann, 2005; Kokou and Sokpon, 2006). The climate change has influenced the country since 1970, with wide spatio-temporal variability.

Soil degradation, desertification and deterioration of grasslands and water resources have been ascribed to these changes (Paturel *et al.* 1998; Gauthier *et al.* 1998; Parry *et al.* 2007). Fears are strongest with respect to water resources which are the life-blood of the economies of West African countries (Kunstmann and Junge, 2005). Crop production and animal husbandry, Benin's main economic activities, find it difficult to coexist due to intense competition for water, making interactions and exchanges between actors more difficult (De Haan *et al.* 1990; McCarthy *et al.* 2001; Morton, 2006). Several bloody conflicts have been recorded between crop producers and livestock herders in northern Benin, which receives each year numerous foreign livestock from bordering countries like Niger, Burkina Faso and Nigeria. The available statistics

reveal 90 deaths from different herder-farmer confrontations in Benin from 1986 to 1994, which led to the closure of the national borders to foreign herds in 1995. Moreover, 1,064 conflicts were recorded between the same actors from 2004 to 2007 in the northern part of the country (MAEP, 2007).

The literature shows that many policies were formulated to curb the increasing farmer-herder conflicts (Hussein *et al.* 1999). In 2004, following the decision of members of ECOWAS States (C/REG.3/01/03) on the mobility of animals and herders, the ministers of ECOWAS States defined five international transhumance routes approved for movement of herds and where fighting should be reduced. However, the conflicts have continued unabated in the ECOWAS zone. From 2009 to 2010, it was found that herders experienced scarcity of natural resources and hence developed various adaptive strategies in the context of climate change (Djohy *et al.* 2011). Knowing that adaptation, a response to specific problems such as climate variability, is considered an evolutionary behavior, we have opted for determining some of the endogenous technical knowledge which the herders have applied in the management of natural resources scarcity for living, moving and producing livestock in a precarious environment. In light of the ECOWAS policy of route formalization, this paper analyses the itinerant herders' strategies of response to the water resource challenges they face along their routes during migration.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

This study was carried out in the Department of Alibori in northern Benin; bounded to the West by Burkina Faso and to the East by Niger and Nigeria. The populations involved are essentially "Bariba", "Fulani" and "Dendi" ethnolinguistic groups. The main economic activities in the study area are crop and animal production. Forest reserves occupy 412,422 hectares (ha) and "W" Park is an important cross-border reserve (MAEP, 2007). Alibori is the zone of highest national livestock concentration containing 692,210 of the national bovine population of 2,058,000 (FAO, 2013). It is also a preferred grazing area for foreign herders from Burkina Faso, Niger and Nigeria due to the good quality pasture and the availability of some periodic or permanent watering sources (Figure 1). Alibori is also an important livestock market area managed by the herders themselves under the Direction of the Departmental Union of Professional Organizations of Herders (UDOPER). Route N°4, one of the five internationally defined routes by ECOWAS, was studied from Malanville district to

Gogounou district while passing by Kandi district in Benin on about 260km.

Data collection

From February to May 2012, 30 herds were purposely followed part of the way along route N°4. The herders encountered during field work were sampled and questions were asked about their country of origin, the livestock weight, the natural resources, especially water and fodder, they used during movement and the duration of pastoral stay. The survey combines semi-structured interviews and focus group. A total of 75 actors were interviewed of whom 30 were herders, 27 farmers and 18 other persons (foresters, water management committee members, landlords, etc.). The national authority of agriculture, environment and water resources and their regional offices were also investigated to understand their policies on this pastoral route. The qualitative data gathered were submitted to discourse analysis in order to construct different aspects of thinking and acting. Herders' decision rules were described and visualized using Star-UML software.

Quantitative data such as on perception radius, stay duration, number of conflicts, and qualitative (type of herders, types of pasture, types of water resources, climate) were computed and integrated into the Common Resources Management Agent-based System (CORMAS). CORMAS is a platform built by the Green Team of CIRAD for representing and simulating the interactions between local actors with diverging interests (Bousquet and Le Page, 2004). The rains started early in 2012 along the study corridor, but the survey took place during a short dry spell. The authors have also simplified some interactions in order to better describe the herders' coping strategies.

Computational modeling

Environment of pastoral water access model "SimWater"

A 50*50 km homogeneous environment was created. There, the various types of grazing area and watering points for herds were randomly distributed as shown in Figure 2. Each space unity is equivalent to 1*1km. The interactions were mostly reduced in order to better describe herders' movement strategies which are highly linked to availability of water and pasture as well as the risk of conflict among farmers, foresters, and even other herders. In the beginning, grazing area and water resources were available for all herders. The scenarios were then enhanced on progressive variations of the quantity and availability of these two critical resources during drought and persistent aridity in the study area.

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Figure 1. Pastoral resources along the studied route N°4/ECOWAS

Model agents: herders and herds

The herders and their animals are the two main agents considered in the production route. The model eliminates the possibility of livestock straying into farmers' fields, meaning that each herd is always under the control of its shepherd (Figure 2). The agents "herders" of this system are defined as having the same attributes except some pastoral considerations and location such as perception of available resources, perception radius, and

resources use stay, etc. The agents' rationalization of certain resource use options and choices have also been simplified. The interactions with farmers and other actors are summarized in order to present the movement logic according to the strategies of each type of herder. In this model only bovine livestock is considered. The dynamics of the flocks do not consider the manure, births, deaths, trade or other events which can increase or reduce the number of animals during the migration.

Figure 2. Unified modeling diagram for SimWater

Model resources: water resources and pasture

All pastoral resources were categorized by actors themselves during data collection (Table 1). Grazing areas are considered as having equal nutritional value, and being otherwise similar in all respects except size. Although herders on transhumance value crop residues, agriculture is completely simplified in this model and considered as generating grazing areas of identical value to the natural vegetation. The growing period of the vegetation was not counted because animal movements are expected to occur in dry season. The water resources are differentiated and considered. The level of water use is not the same for all the flocks; this explains the predilection of different herders according to their flock. Each unit “water reserve” is liable to the same random factor “climate” which can cruelly affect water resources because of the dry season prolongation and any

time lags in the rainy season due to climate variability.

Model dynamic and scenarios

The model is constructed over the great transhumance period from December to July, making a total duration of seven months (210 days). The time step is daily. The dynamics of the model are essentially based on the dynamics of flocks and pastoral resources (water and pasture) under the influence of climate variability and the adaptation strategies of different herders. Two scenarios were developed: a Normal Climate Scenario (NCS) and a Varied Climate Scenario (VCS). The differences between the two scenarios are related to the influence of climate variability according to herders themselves and some directly observed parameters (Table 2).

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Table 1. Characteristics of sampled agents and resources

Agents and Resources	Types	Characteristics
Migratory herders	Large Scale Herders (LSH) or <i>Owoodinai</i> "He has cattle"	05 LSH Herd ≥ 100 (<i>one or more herd</i>)
	Medium Scale Herders (MSH) or <i>Owoodiseeda</i> "He has little"	14 MSH 20 ≤ Herd < 100
	Small Scale Herders (SSH) or <i>Owooda</i> "He has nothing"	11 1 ≤ herd < 20
Pasture Sizes	Large Pasture (LPA) or " <i>Fetore Tobipoui</i> "	01 Park 'W' 01 Djona cynegetics areas 05 State forests (Goungoun, Sota, Kandi, Alibori Supérieur, Trois Rivières)
	Medium Pasture (MPA) or " <i>Fetore Tobiseeda</i> "	Other natural spaces not covered by crops Spaces out of crop or abandoned
	Small Pasture (SPA) or " <i>Fetore Tobaiyori</i> "	Crop spaces and surrounding fields Post-crop residues and vicinities
Water points	Big Water Source (BWS) or " <i>Dianpoui</i> " or " <i>Welere</i> "	04 permanent rivers (Niger, Alibori, Mékrou, Sota) 07 large dams
	Medium Water Source (MWS) or " <i>Dianseeda</i> " or " <i>Belee</i> "	Non permanent rivers 05 backwaters 2000 ha of shallows 01 cascade 28 water collectors.
	Small Water Source (SWS) or " <i>Dianpete</i> " or " <i>Beelee</i> "	11 pastoral tanks 156 artesian wells 28 creeks 320 overdigging wells.

Table 2. Hypotheses and realities defining the two scenarios

Parameters	Normal Climate Scenario (NCS)	Varied Climate Scenario (VCS).
Number of Animals	Three types of herds (LSH, MSH & SSH) are really met in the route N°4	Half of the total number of LSH leaves the route by <i>Confiage</i> ¹ and <i>Habbanae</i> ² contracts, considerably reducing their flocks' number.
Water Availability	Three categories of water sources: (BWS, MWS & SWS) are available	SWS are completely dried up after one additional month of normal dry season and half of the MWS disappeared after two abnormal dry months
Pasture Availability	Three types of pasture resources (LPA, MPA & SPA) are still available for herds.	SPA lack fodder for feeding the herds, but the use of food complementation and accessing the area of " <i>Echinochloa stagnina</i> " make it possible to satisfy herds in fodder. Overdigging strategy prevails.

RESULTS

Herders' decision rules and strategies

Three different strategies were noted amongst the groups of herders who accompany their flocks, grazing over a more or less remote area along route N°4 of ECOWAS (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Decision process for pastoral resources access

Access to resources by LSH: “observe and briefly stay”

Owoodinaï herders' movements are based on observations and assumptions of water availability and access to it. This group of herders has the capability to track long distances by choice. One LSH could move up to 5km, observing and selecting abundant grazing area and water points sufficient to cover the needs of his big flock. When LSHs realize their animals' watering need they will first look for an abundant water source. They operate a dual mode of choice depending of resources availability. Between the three categories of water points, they prefer respectively the big and the medium. Once they find such water points, they water animals and then continue in search of new grazing areas. When resources are abundant in one area, they stay for a maximum of four days to prevent probable insecurity (theft, water poisoning) and other risks related to a long stay. No matter the appetency level of the animals toward some type of fodder, the lack of water reduces their grazing duration. Thus, they undertake transhumance over long distances along route N°4 and follow some secondary pathways in the forests or particular zones (Valley of Niger, Goungoun, Ouémé Supérieur, Alibori Supérieur, Ouénou-Bénou, Trois Rivières, Sota, etc.).

Access to resources by MSH: “observe, stay and contract”

The MSH strategy involves using a combination of natural spaces and farm harvest residues (rice and other cereals, groundnut and gardens residues) for optimal satisfaction of the herds. Herders' strategies are geared towards facilitating timely return back to their semi-permanent residential huts in their communities to watch over the family and get ready for the upcoming farming season. Therefore, a typical MSH does not move beyond 2km and selects the nearest pasture and water points. If the pasture is natural, he lets his animals graze adequately to meet their needs, determines their water need by their behavior and decides whether to let them continue grazing or not. He stays for a maximum of three days in the same zone, grazing and watering. If the rangeland is artificial (harvest residues), he contracts with farmers by paying them money (pecuniary contract) or is temporarily stationary so that the animals can feed on crop land (manure contract). In this case he takes time to move the flock to other sites for watering. Corraling contract is another arrangement with payment in kind to farmers. Animals graze on fields for crop residues and stay overnight on them depositing dung to fertilize the soil.

Access to resources by SSH: “observe, stay, contract and market”

A key coping strategy of the SSH is to explore the possibility of combining the sale of cattle with the search for pasture and water during the transhumance journeys. Many herders in this category have few cattle due to the effects of successive epizootics, climatic crises and unfavourable inheritance conditions. They restrict their movement to less than 2km to grazing areas close to livestock markets. If the nearest pasture is close to a zone of harvest, they engage in a contract of pasture and choose some cattle not necessarily for selling, but also and especially to maintain their position in livestock markets as mediator for merchandising animals for purchasers and sellers that request their expertise. They could dig some water points for their cattle. When a SSH finds a livestock market, he will enter into a crop residues contract with farmers, leave the flock and go to market. He stays for a day and then continues to prospect for resources and market opportunities.

Impacts of strategies on migration paths**Impact on mobility distance**

The adaptive strategies increase pastoral distance (Djohy *et al.* 2013) and the traveled distance depends on the herd size respectively for Normal Climate Scenario (NCS) and Varied Climate Scenario (VCS). LSH and MSH travel further in 210 days than SSH under NCS: When the length of the dry season increases under VCS; all herders travel significantly further (ANOVA $p=0.01$), but LSH and MSH more so than SSH.

At the beginning of great transhumance in the dry season, most of the medium water points contain enough water and all LSH and MSH used them. This explains why they almost travelled the same distance. However, when the length of the dry season increases, these water resources lack abundant quantity and only the medium herds easily access them. The LSHs therefore intensified their search and travelled over longer distance. This explains why they become dominant in VCS.

For SSH, migration distance along the route N°4 is stabilised at an average of 262.5km. There is no statistical significant difference in the distance no matter the aridity of the climatic conditions. This is explained by their decision to sell cattle as another coping strategy. This is an especially important strategy for *Fulbe*. Large numbers of movements are observed around the large cattle markets of Gogounou (terminal zone) situated at about 260 km from the entrance zone.

Impact on visited water resources

The number of water points used during the great transhumance according to the type of herd

has increased respectively under NCS and VCS (Djohy *et al.* 2013). To satisfy their herd's need for water under NCS, the LSH go through 42 watering sources during the entire pastoral season, while the MSH and SSH visited 53 and 70 sources respectively. These numbers remained similar under VCS. The number of browsed water points is not very different in the two scenarios, in spite of the increased transhumance distances in dry season. This can be explained by the fact that in terminal areas, the herders overdig some dried water points and stay much longer than they would usually have. The SSH undertake livestock trade in Gogounou district which is known as the biggest livestock market in Alibori Department. The LSH would either stabilize in the valleys of permanent rivers or deviate from the formal route N°4 of ECOWAS. It can be concluded that the increasing of travelled distance is not proportional to an increase in the observed watering sources.

DISCUSSION

Pastoralism, the use of extensive grazing on rangelands for livestock production, is an important economic activity for between 100 and 200 million people throughout the world. Some socio-cultural norms and values and indigenous knowledge revolve around livestock production (Nusrat, 2012). Pastoral people develop and preserve traditional knowledge associated with their livestock (Raziq *et al.* 2012). Migratory husbandry is the major way pastoralists survive and sustain the ecological balance of nature on account of their dependence on livestock, pasture and water (Bassett 1986; Scoones 1995; Patil *et al.* 2012; Oteros-Rozas *et al.* 2012). It remains a good strategy to keep livestock production viable (Kakar *et al.* 2011). In African countries, animal migratory husbandry occupies a very important position in the socio-cultural milieu. This challenges and renders almost irrelevant all analysis and actions aimed at replicating the ranching systems existing in developed nations (Gefu and Gilles, 1990; Olesen *et al.* 2000). The globalisation-directed policies and programmes which appear insensitive towards the cultural heritage and people's rich experience in conservation-based livelihood systems induce the degradation of cultural and pastoral livelihood options (Nusrat, 2012). For the herders, the changes in mobility pattern proceed from the requirement to preserve a cultural inheritance that is facing persistent environmental and socioeconomic challenges and to meet the obligations towards their households.

If water is a great challenge for extensive animal production systems (Abdullaev *et al.* 2009; Martius *et al.* 2009; Winckler *et al.* 2012), pastoralists have to look to the future and execute a good adaptation strategy. The loss of animals in a context of limited access to water resources due to climate change is unacceptable to future generations. With 107

animals, Sir B.S. who was interviewed around the village of Bagou (district of Gogounou) affirmed:

"We have an obligation to bequeath healthy and productive herds to our children. ...they will not forgive us on the plea of climate change. We have to make up our mind about the future of our children, our culture and our society. We are pastoralists means also that we endure to face every challenge..."

This way of thinking justifies why, despite increasingly constraining and depending on the number of the herds, herders have to increase travelled distance to cover animals' resource needs. For them, this contributes to survival. They therefore believe that migration is predominantly short term, as in the case of extreme weather events and natural disasters, and short distance, as in the case of drought and land degradation (Tacoli, 2009). The use of different areas is a pastoral coping strategy that safeguards the livelihoods of herders and their households (Kreutzman, 2012). In Eastern Africa, the distances moved were found to be significantly correlated to drought and non-drought climatic regimes. Every year, the distance moved is dictated by a complex set of rules that might include religious rites, forage availability, security concerns and/or water availability (Macopiyo, 2005).

Because of the uncertainty involved in advancing to the next potential resource access point, herders stay as long as possible around villages to use crop residues there. However, relations between farmers and herders are often poor; so they manage the length of their stay carefully in order to avoid incidents such as the theft or poisoning of livestock. The herder A.M. having 83 heads of cattle, met one afternoon around the village of Bodjekali (district of Malanville) during the study affirmed:

"We maximize water use before advancing because we don't know what will happen. We take more care about sick and disabled animals and we make reserve for them. But we don't stay too long for reasons of security. It is so a misfortune for you with a big herd, you get too used to the same area. People are going to cause you unnecessary problems. If you are not ransomed for imprecise reasons, a part of your herd is going to perish..."

The social relationship between farmers and pastoralists is recognised as changing and conflict prone (Dyer and Choksi, 2006; Nusrat, 2012). However, even if they represent antagonist groups, farmers and pastoralists along route N°4 remain linked by real contracts of access to crop residues. These contracts are possible especially in situations where farmers do not have personal herds or when the quantity of residues is more than the few plough

oxen can eat. Adaptation measures to cope with climate severity are increasing the capacity of herders to face pasture challenges and access to water resources along the route.

The existence of livestock markets along the route is an important factor for small scale herders' adaptation to water resources access. In fact, the long distances that the pastoralists must travel and the poor infrastructure results in high transaction costs complicating the market exchange (Scoones 1995). Some more vulnerable herders find the market of cattle a good opportunity to make money by selling vulnerable individuals at reduced price. The herder called "dilani" takes advantage of information asymmetry at the local animal market to improve his financial position. Sir H.T., owner of a herd of 17 and "dilani" met during the study in the cattle market of Angaradebou (district of Kandi), explained:

"I don't have a big herd anymore. I must guarantee resources for my animals not to lose them completely. I must face the needs of my household. ...Facing all that, I am obliged to combine other activities. The work of "dilani" is very good and returns me a lot of profit. I earn a lot of money that I use to pay for water where natural water points are completely dried up. When I am at end of the route and also have limited access to a livestock market and I lack water for animals, I am obliged to overdig the pools...".

Regarding the precarious conditions of SSH, this new form of access to the market as "Intermediate seller" or "Intermediate purchaser" is an endogenous adaptation measure by pastoralists in the context of climate scarcity along route N°4. Thus, it is very likely that the current trends of high mobility, linked to income diversification, will continue and intensify (Tacoli, 2009). The over-excitation of the degraded water resources in the terminal area of the route (Figure1) helps the herders to maintain or enhance their access to water. This shows that finding and utilizing reliable water supplies for communities is important (Inverarity *et al.* 2012). The numerical control of animals for pasture management is a good proposition for coping with harsh climate conditions along the study route (Winckler *et al.* 2012).

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATION

The findings underline the "make-or-break" or "do-or-die" logic of pastoralists over depleting resources. They mobilise all strategies to develop their activities and save their herds which eventually will be bequeathed to their children. Increasing distance is a way to cope with climate change. In all studied scenarios, it helps pastoralists to improve access to water resources, but remains a priority for LSH. Specifically, contracts with farmers are a good

mechanism for MSH; market access and water overdigging are the way many SSHs tackle climate conditions. The natural resources perception radius and the temporary stay are innovated measures of adaptation toward risk limitation. Government support to pastoralists would reinforce the significance of animal husbandry in national economies. Therefore, improvement in natural resource management and the enhancement of livestock market infrastructure must be given priority. Based on the foregoing, the following constitutes the main policy implications of the study:

The government of Benin Republic should work in concert with other stakeholders to develop a policy oriented towards different categories of herders because their livelihoods and needs are different. There is a need to carry out a census of national herds in the three districts of study and locate them, as this will ensure the control of foreign herds and their acceptance on the basis of local resources states and availabilities.

The authorities in Benin should regulate the entrance of foreign herds (MSH and LSH notably) to Alibori during harsh climatic conditions to reduce vulnerability of local herds.

It is imperative to increase the number of extension workers so that more effective technical monitoring and control of herds along the migration routes can be planned and executed.

The Benin government should work with ECOWAS to better re-count the local dynamics of actors along route N°4 and all secondary corridors leading to this main corridor.

The national and provincial governments should arrange pastoral resources (water and pasture) every 3km. This is because 3km is the mean perception distance of all herders. Because the distance between the entry and the stopping zone is about 260km, about 87 water and pasture points are required to increase access to these crucial resources and reduce conflicts. Also, they should develop livestock markets and increase supervision over their management with actors. This means that ECOWAS route N°4 as well as the districts along should be equipped and supervised.

There should be a review of legal instruments on transhumance. Most, which formally recognise the pastoral "contracts" between actors, are now outdated.

There is a need to provide more structures for water supply and make them more accessible to herders and inform actors about the necessity of reducing transhumance conflicts and the preservation of herders.

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ENDNOTES

¹. Confiage is a contract in which one gives a part or whole his livestock to another.

². Habbanae consists of leaving some cattle to a brother or friend who will integrate them into his own or given livestock. This contract is emblematic of the solidarity links between fulani herders. It is practiced on route N°4, reducing the number of herds to adapt to climate variability that considerably affects the pastoral resources (Djohy, 2010).

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

This paper is a set of data coming directly out of our study in northern Benin. A part of the results has been communicated at World Impact 2013 Conference in Germany and published afterwards as short conference paper in the Journal of Livestock Science. Never the paper as it is has been edited elsewhere.

REFERENCES

Abdullaev, I., Manthritlake, H., Kazbekov, J., 2009. Water and geopolitics in Central Asia: 125-144. In: *Arsel M., Spoor M. (Eds), Water, environmental security and sustainable rural development: conflict and cooperation in Central Eurasia*, Routledge, New York, USA, 256p.

Arora, M., Singh, P., Goel, N.K., Singh, R.D., 2008. Climate variability influences on hydrological responses of a large Himalayan basin. *Water Resource Management*, 22 (2008):1461–1475.

Barnett, T.P., Adam, J.C., Lettenmaier, D.P., 2005. Potential impacts of a warming climate on water availability in snow-dominated regions. *Nature*, 438: 303-309.

Bassett, T.J., 1986. Fulani herd movements. *The Geographical Review* 76: 233–248.

Bokonon-Ganta, E.B., 1987. *Les climats de la région du Golfe du Bénin (Afrique Occidentale)*. Thèse de doctorat du 3ème cycle, Paris IV-Sorbonne, France, 248p.

Bousquet, F., Le Page, C., 2004. Multi-agent simulations and ecosystem management: a review. *Ecological Modelling* 176 (3–4): 313–332.

De Haan, L.J.de., Driel, A. van, Kruithof, A., 1990. From symbiosis to polarization?: peasants and pastoralists in northern Benin. *Indian Geog Journal*, 65 (1):51-65.

Djohy, G., Edja, A.H., Akponikpè, P.I., Olokesusi, F., Mahamadou, B., 2013. Thwarting social conflicts regarding water resources access in climate change

context: cattle pastoralists' schemes in northern Benin. *Journal of Livestock Science*, 4: 51-59.

Djohy, G., Edja, H., Houinato, M., 2011. The socio-political dynamics of the adaptation of migratory herdsmen to climate change in the North of Benin: 25. In: *AfricaAdapt Climate Change Symposium Proceedings "New voices, different perspectives"*, IDS, UK, 117p.

Dyer, C., Cholski, A., 2006. "With God's Grace and with Education, we will find a Way". In: *Dyer C. (Eds), The Education of Nomadic Peoples Current Issues Future Perspectives*, Berghahn Books, New York (USA) & Oxford (UK), 288p.

FAO, 2013. Statistiques locales, Bénin: Elevage, total des effectifs des animaux vivants par année et par niveau administratif. <http://www.countrystat.org> (accessed 15.02.2013).

Gauthier, F., Lubes-Niel, H., Sabatier, R., Masson, J. M., Paturel, J. E., Servat, E., 1998. Variabilité du régime pluviométrique de l'Afrique de l'Ouest non sahélienne entre 1950 et 1989. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 43(6): 921-935.

Gefu, J.O.; Gilles, J.L., 1990. Pastoralists, ranchers and the state in Nigeria and North America: a comparative analysis. *Nomadic Peoples*, 25-27 (1990): 34-50.

Gorbachev, M., Severino, J-M., 2007. *Climate change and water security*. Project Syndicate, <http://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/climate-change-and-water-security> (accessed 12/10/2012).

Hayward, D., Oguntoyinbo, J., 1987. *The climatology of West Africa*. Rowman & Littlefield, Washington DC, USA, 271p.

Hendrix, C.S., Salehyan, I., 2012. Climate change, rainfall, and social conflict in Africa. *Journal of Peace Research*, 49(1): 35–50.

Hussein, K., Sumberg, J., Seddon, D., 1999. Increasing Violent Conflict between Herders and Farmers in Africa: Claims and Evidence. *Development Policy Review*, 17 (1999): 397–418.

Inverarity, K., Heinson, G., Pedler-Jones, D., Costar, A., Wurst S., McLean G., Simmons, C., 2011. South Australia: Locating Groundwater Resources for Aboriginal Communities in Remote and Arid Parts of South Australia. *The Leading Edge*, 30(4): 402-408.

Kakar, A. R., Verdier, K., Younas, M., 2011. Rapid change of strategy is necessary for development of dromedary camel pastoralism in the Cholistan desert of Pakistan. *Pastoralism: Research, Policy and Practice* 2011 (1): 3.

Kokou, K., Sokpon, N., 2006. Les forêts sacrées du couloir du Dahomey. *Bois et Forêts des Tropiques*, 288 (2):15-23.

Kreutzmann, H., 2012. *Pastoral Practices in High Asia: Agency of 'development' Effected by Modernisation, Resettlement and Transformation*.

Springer Science & Business Media, Berlin, Germany, 350p.

Kunstmann, H., Junge, G., 2005. Regional Hydrological Impacts of Climate Change: impact assessment and decision making. *IAHS Publ*, 295: 75-85.

Lioubimtseva, E., Henebry, G., 2009. Climate and environmental change in arid Central Asia: impacts, vulnerability, and adaptations. *Jour of Arid Env* 73(11): 963–977.

Macopiyo, L. A., 2005. *Spatially explicit, individual-based modelling of pastoralists' mobility in the rangelands of East Africa.* PhD Dissertation, Texas A&M University, USA, 140p.

Madzwamuse, M., 2010. Climate change impacts & vulnerability: 6-13. In: *Madzwamuse, M. (Eds), Climate change vulnerability and adaptation preparedness in South Africa.* Heinrich Böll Stiftung, Cap Town, South Africa, 34p.

MAEP, 2007. *Point Transhumance Transfrontalière de 1995 à 2007.* CeRPA Borgou-Alibori, Ministère de l'Agriculture, de l'Élevage et de la Pêche (MAEP), Cotonou, 27p.

Martius, C., Froebrich, J., Nuppenau, E.A. et al., 2009. Water resource management for improving environmental security and rural livelihoods in the irrigated Amu Darya lowlands: 749-762. In: *Brauch H.G., Oswald S.U., Grin J. (Eds), Facing global environmental change: environmental, human, energy, food, health and water security concepts.* Springer Science & Business Media, Berlin, Germany, 1636p.

McCarthy, J.J., Canziani, O.F., Leary, N.A., Dokken, D.J. and Kasey, S.W., 2001. Climate Change 2001: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. *Contribution of Working Group II to the IPCC Third Assessment Report*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1032p.

Morton, J.F., 2006. Pastoralist coping strategies and emergency livestock market intervention: 227–246. In: *McPeak J.G., Little P.D. (Eds), Pastoral Livestock Marketing in Eastern Africa: Research and Policy Challenges.* Intermediate Technology, London, UK, 288p.

Morton, J.F., 2007. The impact of climate change on smallholder and subsistence agriculture. *PNAS*, 104 (50): 19680-19685.

Nusrat, R., 2012. Changing values among pastoralists of Himalaya in the wake of globalization. *Adv in Agri, Sci & Eng Research*, 2(5): 153-157.

Olesen, I., Groen, A.F., Gjerde, B., 2000. Definition of animal breeding goals for sustainable production systems. *Journal of Animal Sciences*, 78(2000):570-582.

Olorunfemi, F.B., 2011. *Managing flood disasters under a changing climate: lessons from Nigeria and South Africa.* NISER Discussion paper n°1 (2011), Ibadan, Nigeria, 43p.

Oteros-Rozas, E., González, J.A., Martín-López, B., López, C.A., Zorrilla-Miras, P., Montes, C., 2012. Evaluating ecosystem services in transhumance cultural landscapes: an interdisciplinary and participatory framework. *GAIA-GAIA-Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 21(3): 185–193.

Parry, M.L., Canziani, O.F., Palutikof, J.P., van der Linden, P.J., Hanson, C.E., 2007. Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. *Contribution of Working Group II to the IPCC Fourth Assessment Report.* Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 982p.

Patil, D.S., Meena, H.R., Tripathi, H., Kumar, S., Singh, D.P., 2012. Socio-economic profile of sheep reared Dhangar pastoralists of Maharashtra, India. *J Rec Adv Agri*, 1(3): 84-91.

Paturel, J. E., Servat, E., Delattre, M. O., Lubes-Niel, H., 1998. Analyse de séries pluviométriques de longue durée en Afrique de l'Ouest et Centrale non sahélienne dans un contexte de variabilité climatique. *Hydro Sciences Journal*, 43(6): 937-946.

Raziq, A., Tareen, A.M., de Verdier, K., 2012. Characterization and significance of Raigi camel, a livestock breed of the Pashtoon pastoral people in Afghanistan and Pakistan. *Journal of Livestock Science*, 2: 11-19.

Salzmann, U., Hoelzmann, P., 2005. The Dahomey Gap: an abrupt climatically induced rain forest fragmentation in West Africa during the late Holocene. *The Holocene*, 15:190-199.

Scoones, I., 1995. *Living with uncertainty: New directions in pastoral development in Africa (Preface and Chapter One).* Institute of Development Studies (IDS), ITDG, London, UK, 36p.

Tacoli, C., 2009. Crisis or adaptation? Migration and climate change in a context of high mobility. *Environment and Urbanization*, 21(2): 513-525.

Winckler, G., Kleinn, E., Breckle, S-W., 2012. The Aralkum Situation under Climate Change Related to Its Broader Regional Context: 431-456. In: *Breckle S.W. et al. (Eds), Aralkum-a Man-Made Desert: The Desiccated Floor of the Aral Sea (Central Asia).* Ecological Studies 218, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, 486p.

Zhang, Q., Xu, C.Y., Yang, T., 2009. Variability of water resource in the Yellow River Basin of past 50 years, China. *Water Resource Management* 23 (6): 1157–1170.